

Innovative transfer: harnessing automotive technologies for maritime progress

Alexandra Baicoianu¹[0000-0002-1264-3404], Calin Husar¹[0009-0008-5789-7361],

Vlad Solomon¹, Cristi Irimia¹, and Lars-Petter Larsen²

¹ Siemens Industry Software SRL, Brasov, Romania

² Corvus Energy, Bergen, Norway
calin.husar@siemens.com

Abstract. In the last decade, the automotive industry has made significant steps in innovation, particularly in areas such as hybrid and electric propulsion systems, autonomous driving, advanced sensor systems, including smart connectivity. This paper explores the potential of transferring these innovative technologies to the maritime sector for the improvement of maritime technologies. By analyzing key automotive advancements and their applicability to maritime challenges, this paper aims to highlight how such cross-industry innovation can lead to increased efficiency, sustainability, and safety in shipping and marine operations. Considering specific examples it demonstrated how electric propulsion systems, can be adapted for maritime use, ultimately driving the evolution of modern maritime practices and contributing to the development of greener and smarter shipping solutions.

Keywords: Automotive Innovation, Technology Transfer, Maritime Technology

1 Introduction: Bridging Automotive and Maritime Technologies

The rapid advancements in the automotive industry over the past years have highly revolutionized transportation, bringing forth innovations that have significantly enhanced safety, vehicles efficiency and hence environmental sustainability - a very discussed aspect nowadays. As the world increasingly emphasizes the importance of technological advancements and sustainable practices, other industries, including the maritime sector, are beginning to look towards more sustainable solutions. The automotive industry is a clear inspiration source due to its validated results in autonomous driving, vehicle connectivity and propulsion systems.

1.1 The Need for Innovation in Maritime Industry

In the latest years, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) [1] highly increased the regulations for the maritime sector, an industry which plays an important role in global trade and transportation, who faces several challenges for which innovative solutions must be found. The environmental impact, fuel efficiency, safety, and operational efficiency are at the forefront of maritime concerns, while the traditional maritime practices and technologies are often insufficient to meet the rising demands for greener, safer, and more efficient operations. This creates a unique opportunity to explore and adapt the technologies validated in automotive industry to address these maritime challenges.

1.2 Historical Perspective: Cross-Industry Innovation

Historically, cross-industry innovation [2] has been a key driver of technological progress. The transfer of technologies and best practices across different sectors has often led to breakthroughs that might not have been possible without cross-collaboration between industries. In the context of automotive and maritime industries, both domains share common or similar technological needs, challenges, and regulations, making them suitable candidates for cross-industry innovation. For instance, both industries require robust and reliable propulsion systems, advanced navigation technologies, sophisticated safety mechanisms and technologies used to decrease pollution.

1.3 Automotive Innovations: A Treasure Trove for Maritime Applications

The automotive industry has been at the forefront of several groundbreaking innovations. Electric propulsion systems combined with internal combustion engines, which have revolutionized the automotive sector by offering cleaner and more efficient alternatives to conventional internal combustion engines, are now being explored for their potential in maritime applications. Similarly, autonomous driving technologies, which rely on advanced sensors and artificial intelligence offer promising solutions for improving autonomous and safer navigation in maritime environments.

In addition to propulsion and navigation, automotive advancements in connectivity and smart systems can significantly enhance maritime operations. Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication [3], which facilitates seamless connectivity between vehicles and infrastructure, can be adapted to create smarter ports and high efficiency shipping logistics. Furthermore, the automotive industry's progress in developing robust safety systems, such as collision avoidance or other emergency response mechanisms, can be instrumental in enhancing maritime safety.

2 Potential Automotive Technologies for Maritime Applications

The automotive industry is well known as a beacon of innovation, continually pushing boundaries and exploring frontiers in new technologies. Many of these advancements can revolutionize other sectors as well, including the maritime one [4], offering solutions to longstanding challenges and driving progress towards a more sustainable and efficient maritime future, with a main goal of reducing the air emission pollutants. Climate degradation is generated by the high amount of CO₂, SO₂, NO₂ and particulate emissions which are caused by traditional high-power engines used to propel the vessels.

2.1 Hybrid and Electric Propulsion Systems

One of the most transformative innovations in the automotive industry is the widespread adoption of hybrid and fully electric propulsion systems. Electric vehicles (EVs) have gained momentum as viable alternatives to traditional internal combustion engine vehicles, offering lower emissions, reduced fuel consumption, and quieter operation. These benefits extend beyond the automotive realm and hold immense promise for the maritime sector.

Electric propulsion systems for ships, often referred to as electric propulsion or electric drive systems, utilize electric motors powered by batteries or fuel cells [5] to propel vessels. By replacing conventional diesel engines with electric propulsion, ships can significantly reduce their environmental footprint, particularly in terms of greenhouse gas emissions and air pollution. Additionally, electric propulsion systems offer improved efficiency and lower operating costs compared to traditional propulsion methods [6], but at a higher production cost.

2.2 Autonomous Navigation Technologies

The development of autonomous driving technologies represents another frontier in automotive innovation with vast potential for maritime navigation applications. Autonomous vehicles (AVs) leverage a combination of sensors such as cameras, radars, lidars, and artificial intelligence to navigate and operate vehicles without human intervention. While autonomous cars have garnered significant attention, the principles underlying autonomous driving can be adapted to maritime environments, paving the way for autonomous vessels.

Autonomous navigation systems for ships revolutionize maritime transportation by enhancing safety, efficiency, and reliability. These systems can enable unmanned or minimally staffed vessels to autonomously navigate complex waterways, avoid collisions, and optimize route planning based on real-time data and environmental conditions. By reducing reliance on human operators and mitigating the risk of human error, autonomous navigation technologies can enhance the safety and operational efficiency of maritime industry.

2.3 Industrial Internet of Things for Maritime Industry – Advanced Sensor Networks

The advanced connectivity sensors are standing at the foundation stone of Industrial Internet of Things technologies [7], also known as IoT, who represents a collective network of linked devices, whose goal is to facilitate the communication between them by providing critical information about industrial applications or processes.

As mentioned above, substantial innovations were made into the automotive industry in recent years, and one of the most impactful innovations is represented by the developing of advanced sensor technologies to enable vehicles to perceive and interpret their surroundings accurately. These sensor networks, consisting of cameras, radar, lidar, ultrasonic sensors, and more, provide vehicles with the perception capabilities necessary for autonomous driving and advanced driver assistance systems (ADAS) [8].

By integrating similar sensor networks in maritime applications can unlock new possibilities for enhancing safety, and operational efficiency at the same time. One of the main advantages of such an IoT network can enable ships to monitor their surroundings, detect obstacles, and navigate safely through challenging environments such as busy ports or congested waterways, being in contact with various equipment of vessels located in ports or on the sea. At the same time, crucial data is collected and delivered.

The used sensors can facilitate environmental monitoring as well, allowing ships to assess water quality, detect pollutants, and mitigate potential ecological impacts. By leveraging advanced sensor technologies, maritime operators can gain valuable insights into vessel performance, environmental conditions, and operational parameters, enabling more informed decision-making and proactive risk management, closer to the real time. Connectivity lies at the heart of modern automotive systems, enabling vehicles to communicate with each other, infrastructure, and cloud-based services in real-time. At the same time, connectivity represents one of the main features of internet of things technologies, facilitated by vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) communication, vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communication, and vehicle-to-cloud (V2C) communication, which enables a wide range of safety, navigation, and entertainment features in automobiles. Similar connectivity solutions to vehicle applications could be adopted in maritime industry by enabling ships to communicate to shore-based facilities, and maritime authorities in a safety and highly efficient way.

Proposed smart connectivity solutions for maritime applications can enable real-time data exchange, remote monitoring, and fleet management capabilities, for enhancing situational awareness and operational efficiency. By leveraging IoT cloud-based services and data analytics using large language models, maritime operators can optimize route planning, fuel consumption, and maintenance scheduling, leading to cost savings and environmental benefits.

Additionally, connectivity solutions can facilitate the integration of autonomous navigation systems by using augmented reality technologies and advanced sensor networks, enabling seamless communication and coordination between autonomous and traditional vessels.

3 Showcase examples: Real-World Applications

Examining real-world case studies and exploring prospects is essential for understanding the practical implications and potential of transferring automotive technologies to the maritime sector. The case-studies listed below are part of the EU project Nemoship [10], project which has the ambition to develop, test, demonstrate new innovative technologies, methodologies and guidelines to better optimize large electric battery power technology within hybrid and fully electrical ships.

3.1 Example 1: Hybrid Propulsion in Le Commandant Charcot

The hybrid propulsion system of the polar exploration vessel, Le Commandant Charcot [9], provides an exemplary case of integrating automotive-inspired technology into maritime applications. Operated by Ponant, this vessel combines liquefied natural gas (LNG) and electric battery power to create a hybrid propulsion system. This innovative setup allows for a significant reduction in emissions, enhanced fuel efficiency, and quieter operation, essential for environmentally sensitive polar regions.

Le Commandant Charcot is equipped with advanced battery systems that enable the vessel to operate in electric mode for extended periods, reducing reliance on conventional fuel and minimizing environmental impact, see Fig.1. The hybrid system ensures that the vessel can navigate through ice-covered waters with precision and reliability, leveraging the combined power of LNG and electricity for optimal performance.

This case study highlights the successful implementation of hybrid propulsion systems, showcasing the potential for combining traditional maritime propulsion with electric power derived from automotive advancements. The operational success of Le Commandant Charcot demonstrates how hybridization can be effectively utilized in maritime applications, paving the way for further adoption of hybrid systems in other types of vessels.

Fig. 1: The newly designed "Le Commandant Charcot" vessel owned by Ponant

3.2 Example 2: Retrofitting Normand Drott with Hybrid Technology

The retrofitting of the offshore supply vessel (OSV) Normand Drott [11] with hybrid technology represents another significant example of applying automotive-inspired innovation in the maritime sector. Operated by Solstad Offshore, Normand Drott, see Fig. 2, is planning to be retrofitted during 2024 year with a battery pack system that allows the vessel to operate in hybrid mode, combining traditional diesel engines with battery power. This retrofit is part of a larger initiative to reduce fuel consumption and emissions while enhancing operational flexibility.

The hybrid system planned to be installed on Normand Drott includes advanced energy storage solutions that will enable the vessel to optimize power usage during various operational modes, such as dynamic positioning, transit, and standby. By integrating battery power, the vessel will reduce engine running hours, leading to lower maintenance costs and extended engine life. Additionally, the hybrid system will provide a significant reduction in greenhouse gas emissions and noise pollution, making the vessel more environmentally friendly and suitable for operations in sensitive areas.

This case study plans to demonstrate the feasibility and benefits of retrofitting existing vessels with hybrid technology, highlighting the potential for widespread adoption across the maritime industry. The success of Normand Drott's retrofit will showcase how existing maritime assets can be upgraded to meet modern environmental and operational standards, contributing to a more sustainable and efficient maritime sector.

Fig. 2: The retrofitted "Normand Drott" vessel owned by Solstad

3.3 Example 3: Electric Propulsion in Ferries

One compelling case study of leveraging automotive technology in the maritime sector is the adoption of electric propulsion systems in ferries. Several ferry operators worldwide have embraced electric propulsion to reduce emissions, improve efficiency, and enhance passenger experience. For example, the "Ampere [12]," operated by Norled in Norway, is the world's first all-electric ferry, powered by batteries and equipped with fast-charging stations at each port. The success of the "Ampere" demonstrates the feasibility and benefits of electric propulsion in maritime applications, inspiring other ferry operators to follow suit and invest in cleaner, more sustainable propulsion technologies.

3.4 Future Prospects and Emerging Trends

Looking ahead, several emerging trends and future prospects are shaping the landscape of automotive technology transfer in the maritime sector. One notable trend is the convergence of electric propulsion, autonomous navigation, and connectivity solutions to create integrated smart ship systems. These systems leverage the collective capabilities of electric propulsion systems, autonomous navigation technologies, and advanced sensor networks to optimize vessel performance, enhance safety, and reduce environmental impact.

Another promising area is the development of hybrid propulsion systems that combine electric and conventional propulsion methods to achieve greater flexibility and efficiency. Hybrid propulsion systems offer the benefits of both electric and traditional propulsion, allowing ships to operate in a wider range of conditions while minimizing emissions and fuel consumption.

Furthermore, the increasing focus on sustainability and environmental stewardship is driving demand for innovative solutions such as hydrogen fuel cells and alternative fuels. Hydrogen fuel cells hold promise as a clean and renewable energy source for maritime propulsion, offering zero-emission operation and long-range capabilities.

4 Conclusions

The convergence of automotive and maritime technologies presents unprecedented opportunities for innovation and progress in the maritime sector. By leveraging the advancements made in electric propulsion, autonomous navigation, advanced sensor networks, and smart connectivity solutions, maritime operators can address longstanding challenges and drive transformative change.

Throughout this paper, we have explored the potential of transferring automotive technologies to the maritime domain, examining how electric propulsion systems can reduce emissions and improve efficiency, how autonomous navigation technologies can enhance safety and operational efficiency, and how advanced sensor networks and connectivity solutions can enable smarter and more connected maritime operations.

Real-world case studies have demonstrated the feasibility and benefits of adopting automotive technologies in maritime applications, from the deployment of electric ferries to the trials of autonomous shipping vessels. These examples underscore the tangible impact that cross-industry innovation can have on the maritime industry, driving progress towards a more sustainable, efficient, and safe maritime future.

Looking ahead, emerging trends such as the integration of hybrid propulsion systems, the development of hydrogen fuel cells, and the convergence of smart ship systems offer exciting prospects for further innovation and advancement. By embracing these trends and fostering collaboration between the automotive and maritime sectors, we can accelerate the transition towards a greener, smarter, and more sustainable maritime transportation ecosystem.

In conclusion, the transfer of automotive technologies to the maritime sector holds immense promise for addressing the challenges facing the maritime industry and

unlocking new opportunities for growth and prosperity. As we continue to explore and harness the synergies between these two industries, we can chart a course towards a brighter maritime future, where sustainability, efficiency, and safety are paramount.

Acknowledgments. The NEMOSHIP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101096324. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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